

A Chromatographic Study of some Reactive Dyestuff

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QUITE recently I.C.I., Ciba and Farbwerke Hoechst have put on the market a series of chemically reactive dyestuff. These dyestuff¹⁻³ have taken up different trade names such as Procion, Cibacron, Remazol etc. These dyestuff have a common property of forming chemical linkages with cellulose in alkaline medium. But in neutral medium there is practically no chemical activity with cellulose. Moreover, in alkaline solution the reactive dyes gets hydrolysed and the products of hydrolysis have no substantivity for cellulose fibre.

In the present work a study is made to determine the optimum pH values for dyeing cellulose; for Procion brilliant red H8B, Procion yellow M4R, Procion brilliant red M2B and Cibacron brilliant red 5BE.

Experimental

Keeping the unique characteristic properties of the reactive dyes, it was thought that chromatographic study of these dyes as a function of pH would lead to interesting information of optimum pH values of these dyes for dyeing cellulose. Circular paper chromatographic study of the dyes was made using 12.5 cm diameter Whatman No. 1 filter paper discs using Rutter's method⁴. Buffer solutions ranging from 2 to 10 pH were used as developing solutions. 0.2% of aqueous solutions of the commercial dyes were used. All the dyes used were cold brand reactive dyes. After marking the edges of the different zones, the active hydrolysed dye was removed by soaping and boiling the chromatograms. 'R' values, defined as ratio of distance travelled by the dye to that travelled by the solvent, was determined at various pH values ranging from 2 to 10 pH. A graph of 'R' values versus pH was drawn.

Discussion

These reactive dyes are prepared by linking cyanuric chloride with azo or anthraquinone dyes which has an amino group. The dyes so formed have two labile chlorine atoms, and these auxochromes are available for chemical combination with cellulose.

As these dyes are cold brand used for dyeing cotton between 8 to 9 pH, sharp minimum between 8 to 9 pH was expected. It is interesting to note that all figures show three minimas. All show optimum pH 8. As there are two reactive 'Cl' atoms, and as the reactivity of these 2 'Cl' atoms being different we may expect two minimas. To account for three minimas, argument given by Sivarajan and Parikh⁶ has been extended to explain the observation of more than one minima.

The reactive dye partly reacts with the cellulose of the Whatman filter paper and forms a chemically fixed coloured zone. A part of the dye gets hydrolysed, the hydrolysed inactive form and the unreacted dye left spreads further as the developing solvent advances forming the outer coloured zones of further chemically combined as well as the adsorbed inactive dye. The extent to which the colour zones spreads and the formation of more than one chemically combined zone depends on the reactivity of the dye, also the affinity of the dye to be adsorbed and depends on the pH of the eluent used.

Minima obtained in 'R' values versus pH graph show optimum pH when maximum percentage fixation of the dye takes place. It is noteworthy that procion dyes have peak fixation values at more than one pH values⁵.

Procion yellow M4R has minima at pH 3, 6 and 9. Procion brilliant red H8B has minima at pH 3, 7 and 9. Procion brilliant red M2B has minima at pH 4, 6, 8 and beyond pH 10, while Cibacron brilliant red 5B-E has minima at pH 4, 6 and 8. A general conclusion which can be arrived at, is that the reaction rate of the dye with cellulose is dependent on a number of factors and it is not instantaneous¹. The fact that the high values of 'R' are obtained both at high and low pH values. The reaction between the dye and cellulose is not simple. It is still more complex at high alkali concentrations.

A detail study of these at higher pH values will be published elsewhere.

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